

Memorandum in response to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

To: the Clerk of the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
From: M█████ E█████ D█████, Student, University of Cambridge
Subject: the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021
Date: September 30, 2021

I am grateful to your Committee for the chance to submit this memorandum to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill.

As a Ghanaian citizen, I am deeply concerned about the intolerable situation LGBTQ+ Ghanaians are currently facing. The “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021” is a severe violation of basic human rights. The proposed legislation would sentence anyone found to be LGBTQ+, or even an ally, to a prison sentence of up to ten years for what is seen as a second-degree felony. Similarly, providing assistance, services or funding to LGBTQ+ people or groups would be punishable.

This intolerable bill dehumanises LGBTQ+ people in Ghana and puts their lives and safety at risk. It goes against all international standards for human rights. Freedom from discrimination on the grounds of sexual orientation is protected in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as well as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights which Ghana ratified in 2000.

Worryingly, we witness the hollowing out of Ghanaian democracy, the values our forebearers fought so hard to gain – freedom of expression, freedom of information and education, freedom from discrimination and protection against institutional abuse.

The bill violates Article 17 of Ghana’s constitution and Articles 2 and 3 of the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights which Ghana has signed and pledged to uphold. According to Amnesty International, this bill is a “clear violation of the Ghanaian Constitution which universally protects all persons’ rights to freedom of association and expression”. Section 17 of the constitution guarantees human rights for all persons stating “All persons shall be equal before the law”. Article 19 of the constitution states “A person charged with a criminal offence shall be permitted to defend himself before court or by a lawyer of his choice”, something which the bill would deny.

This year, threats and abuses against the LGBTQ+ community have increased, a community centre has been shut down in February, and 21 people were arrested in Ho in March. It is up to lawmakers to ensure that the country lives up to its promise of protecting its citizens.

Homophobic legislation is an antiquated colonial remnant that has outstayed its welcome. Ghana’s achievements since 1975 have instilled me with pride. It has been a frontrunner in the fight for self-determination and equality. It is heart-breaking to see this effort crumble.

Despite aims to attract diasporic Ghanaians to return to and invest in the country, it is impossible for many to feel a sense of belonging if their home country questions their very right to exist and puts their safety at risk.

All over the world, Ghanaians are appalled by the recent developments and have pledged to support the LGBTQ community. We expect that lawmakers who have vowed to protect the lives of all Ghanaians, do the same. I urge you to take responsibility and protect the basic liberties of LGBTQ+ Ghanaians.

Thank you for taking my concerns seriously.

With kind regards,

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